

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH SPEAKING

Oripova Nargiza Vosiqjon qizi

Lecturer of Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Over the past few years, artificial intelligence is spreading over the world, thus a lot of spheres yielding their place to it, where teaching is not an exception. There was composed some professions where the workers that can be replaced either fully or partly by AI, like copywriters, accountant, bank workers, assistants and sometimes even teachers. AI has the potential to greatly impact education by transforming various aspects of the learning process.*

Keywords: natural language processing, feedback, speech patterns, personalized guidance, international collabs, global careers, recognition algorithm, pronunciation errors, system, speaker models, cultural insights

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant advancements in various fields, and one area where it has shown great potential is in teaching and learning languages. AI-powered technologies are being integrated into language education to enhance the learning experience, provide personalized instruction, and improve overall proficiency in a language. “Artificial Intelligence, characterized by its ability to simulate human intelligence, has made significant advancements in recent years, permeating various domains of society” [7]. In this discussion, we will explore the applications of AI in speaking teaching language and how it is revolutionizing language education. It is being used to develop interactive language learning platforms that provide users with personalized lessons, practice exercises, and real-time feedback. These platforms utilize natural language processing (NLP) algorithms to understand and analyze learners' input, allowing for customized learning paths based on individual strengths and weaknesses. The integration of artificial intelligence in learning languages gives tremendous possibilities for developing the 4 basic skills which are reading, writing, listening and speaking.

The ability to communicate clearly and effectively in different languages and especially in English gives a lot of educational opportunities, international collabs, global careers prospects. As the demand for this language is increasing, the instructors, researchers work on exploring innovative approaches to get more language learning outcomes. AI technologies, like speech recognition and natural language processing, enable learners to practice and improve their speaking and listening skills. Speech recognition algorithms can accurately transcribe spoken language, while language processing algorithms can analyze and correct grammar and pronunciation errors. These tools provide learners with real-time feedback and help them refine their language skills. Feedback from the system shows improvements comparing to those who don't after investigating the effectiveness of AI speech recognition [4].

Nowadays modern students prefer to use technology and how their learning, the use of modern equipment, technologies and tools increases the effectiveness of learning and interactivity of students. They also find it much more interactive and fuller of interesting areas, and they involved in class. Knowledge transfer becomes very simple and convenient, as well as effective. This means that our mind now tends to work faster when modern technology helps it, whether in any area of life, as well as education. Relying on innovations, which simply make life easy and smooth, is absolutely inevitable these days, even in schools, universities and colleges. But on the other hand, it can be argued that modern technologies in education sometimes effects on students' imagination and their thinking skills.

Many experts and experienced people say that, due to

AI has the potential to greatly assist in teaching speaking skills. While traditional language teaching methods often focus on reading and writing, AI can offer unique opportunities for practicing and improving spoken language abilities. In practicing pronunciation AI can provide comments on it, helping learners identify and correct errors. By analyzing speech patterns and comparing them to native speaker models, AI can offer personalized guidance to improve pronunciation accuracy. The results of the research done by Chen et al. (2018) shows that usage of AI-based virtual tutors improves learners' fluency and accuracy [1].

It's important to note that while AI can be a valuable tool in language teaching, it cannot replace human teachers. The role of the teacher in providing guidance, motivation, and cultural insights remains crucial in the language learning process. AI should be seen as a complementary tool that enriches the learning experience and supports both learners and teachers.

AI can be utilized in teaching speaking pronunciation practice, conversational agents, speech recognition technology, virtual reality (VR) simulations, intelligent tutoring systems, language assessment

Conversational agents known as chatbots, which engage in interactive conversations with learners, they can simulate real-life language exchanges, and provide learners with opportunities to practice speaking and develop fluency, in addition to it gain confidence during the conversation. The role of AI-based chatbots in language learning and highlighted their ability to provide immediate and interactive language practice opportunities [9].

Furthermore, artificial intelligence can be used to improve speech recognition system which analyze and decode speech. Students easily practice speaking by interacting with this settled systems, which give them immediate comments on their oral responses. These kinds of technologies can be integrated into language learning platforms or mobile apps. “The rapid increase in the utilization of online learning environments and social network sites, such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn offers additional potential for the pedagogical use of peer assessment through feedback” [2].

Nowadays virtual reality is increasing, it can be one of the parts of the teaching, as they can be combined with AI and create immerse language learning environment, providing with the virtual scenarios like places, actions, where they can practice speaking and receive feedback from virtual characters. Benefit of immersion is that it ensures a sense of presence or the feeling that one is really in the depicted world [8]. This allows learners to experience real-life situations without the pressure of face-to-face interaction, which can be very convenient for introvert learners.

There is also AI-tutoring system can analyze student's oral responses guiding and providing personalized feedback. These systems can track progress over time, identify areas for improvement, and offer customized exercises and activities to improve conversational skills. “Through a variety of tools, resources, and the direction of teachers and mentors, technology-supported learning enables students to improve their knowledge and abilities” [3].

Artificial intelligence can assist in evaluating learners' speaking proficiency, fluency, accuracy, vocabulary usage, and other relevant aspects by analyzing spoken responses. This can provide objective and consistent assessment, reducing the subjectivity of human grading.

Offering personalized learning based on each student's strengths and weaknesses and learning style preferences, AI-based learning systems can develop the student learning process. Intelligent teachers and learning analytics can be just two examples of AI-enabled learning systems

that provide personalized feedback and direction to students, greatly enhancing their learning experience. Numerous artificial intelligence-based learning systems, like intelligent tutors and learning analytics, have formed due to advances in artificial intelligence research. And, “these developments have been useful in education, as they provide personalized feedback and recommendations to students, which contributes to a more effective learning process” [6].

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the development of communication skills of English language learners opens up great prospects for improving the results of language learning. It's important to note that while AI can play a valuable role in teaching speaking skills, it should not replace human interaction entirely. Language learning is a social process, and learners benefit from practicing speaking with native speakers and receiving personalized guidance from experienced language teachers. AI should be seen as a complementary tool that enhances language learning experiences.

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